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Маркетингові стратегії як інструмент ефективного антикризового управління підприємствами в умовах трансформації економіки

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Анотація: У статті досліджено сутність, роль та особливості формування маркетингових стратегій у системі управління аграрними підприємствами в умовах нестабільного економічного середовища. Метою дослідження є обґрунтування значення маркетингових стратегій як інструменту забезпечення конкурентоспроможності та сталого розвитку підприємств із урахуванням принципів антикризового управління та проєктного підходу.

Методологічну основу дослідження становлять загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи, зокрема аналіз і синтез, системний підхід, порівняльний аналіз, а також методи стратегічного маркетингу. У роботі досліджено сучасні підходи до формування маркетингових стратегій, визначено їх структурні елементи та етапи реалізації.

У результаті дослідження встановлено, що маркетингова стратегія є ключовим елементом системи управління підприємством, який забезпечує адаптацію до змін зовнішнього середовища, підвищення ефективності використання ресурсів та формування конкурентних переваг. Доведено, що в умовах кризи маркетингові стратегії виступають важливим інструментом мінімізації ризиків та забезпечення стабільності діяльності. Особливу увагу приділено ролі цифрових технологій та проєктного підходу у підвищенні ефективності реалізації маркетингових рішень.

Висновки свідчать про необхідність інтеграції маркетингових стратегій із системою антикризового управління та активного використання сучасних інструментів цифровізації і проєктного менеджменту. Це дозволить підвищити адаптивність аграрних підприємств до змін ринкового середовища, забезпечити їх стійкий розвиток та зміцнити конкурентні позиції.

Ключові слова: маркетингова стратегія, підприємства, антикризове менеджмент, проєктний підхід, цифровий маркетинг, конкурентоспроможність, стратегічне управління, ризики, сталий розвиток

**Marketing strategies as a tool for effective anti-crisis business management
under conditions of economy transformation**

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Abstract: The article examines the essence, role, and features of marketing strategy development within the management system of agricultural enterprises under conditions of economic instability. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the importance of marketing strategies as a tool for ensuring competitiveness and sustainable development, considering the principles of crisis management and the project-based approach.

The methodological basis of the research includes general scientific and special methods, such as analysis and synthesis, a systematic approach, comparative analysis, and strategic marketing methods. The paper explores modern approaches to the formation of marketing strategies, identifies their structural elements, and determines the stages of their implementation.

The results show that a marketing strategy is a key element of enterprise management, ensuring adaptation to environmental changes, improving resource efficiency, and forming competitive advantages. It is proven that under crisis conditions, marketing strategies serve as an important tool for risk minimization and business stability. Special attention is paid to the role of digital technologies and project management in enhancing the effectiveness of marketing decisions.

The conclusions highlight the need to integrate marketing strategies with crisis management systems and actively use modern digital and project management tools. This will increase the adaptability of agricultural enterprises to market changes, ensure sustainable development, and strengthen their competitive positions.

Keywords: marketing strategy, agricultural enterprises, crisis management, project approach, digital marketing, competitiveness, strategic management, risks, sustainable development.

Statement of the problem. In today's economic environment, the effective operation of agricultural enterprises depends to a large extent on the level of organization of their marketing activities, their ability to adapt quickly to changes in the market environment, and their focus on consumer needs. Ukraine's agricultural

sector is undergoing structural transformation, accompanied by increased competition, changing market demands, the active development of digital technologies, and the growing importance of strategic management. Under these conditions, marketing strategies have become a vital tool for ensuring stable development, strengthening competitive positions, and increasing the profitability of enterprises in the agricultural sector.

At the same time, the modern business environment is characterized by a high level of uncertainty, risks, and crises, which necessitates the integration of marketing strategies into a company's crisis management system. It is marketing that serves as a tool for timely response to changes in demand, reassessment of market priorities, diversification of sales channels, and the development of sustainable competitive advantages during crises. An effectively developed marketing strategy allows enterprises not only to minimize the negative consequences of crises but also to use them as an opportunity to update their business model and increase management flexibility.

In modern conditions, the development and implementation of marketing strategies should also be viewed through the lens of a project-based management approach, which involves clear planning, resource allocation, performance monitoring, and evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing initiatives. Marketing project management allows for the systematization of the process of implementing strategic decisions, increasing their effectiveness, reducing costs, and ensuring that set goals are achieved within specified timeframes. The use of project management tools helps increase companies' adaptability to changes in the external environment and ensures their resilience in crisis situations.

Marketing in agriculture plays a special role, as it allows not only for the effective sale of produced goods but also for the formation of strong ties between producers and consumers, the development of flexible pricing policies, the improvement of distribution systems, and the creation of a positive corporate image in the market. In the context of the digital economy, marketing strategies must rely on

modern information technologies, data analytics, e-commerce, and communications, which enable a new level of business process management.

The purpose of this article is to examine the essence, role, and characteristics of marketing strategy development within the management system of agricultural enterprises, considering the principles of anti-crisis management and the project-based approach, as well as to justify their importance for enhancing competitiveness and ensuring sustainable development in a dynamic and risky market environment.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The issue of forming and implementing marketing strategies in the enterprise management system, in particular the agricultural sector, is the subject of active research by both domestic and foreign scientists. Considerable attention is paid to the issues of increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, adapting to changes in the market environment and implementing modern strategic marketing tools, especially in conditions of instability and crisis challenges.

The theoretical principles of marketing management are widely disclosed in the works of F. Kotler and K. L. Keller, Charkina, T. Yu. who consider marketing strategy as a key element of the enterprise management system, focused on meeting consumer needs and achieving long-term development goals [9,10]. Similar approaches are also followed by Ukrainian scientists, in particular L. V. Balabanova, Hramatovych Yu who emphasizes the strategic role of marketing in ensuring the effective functioning of the enterprise [3; 4]. A significant contribution to the development of the theory of marketing activity was made by V. Ya. Kardash, who studies the issues of forming a product policy and the integrated use of marketing tools [7; 8].

In scientific works, considerable attention is paid to determining the essence of marketing strategy, its structural elements and stages of formation. Researchers emphasize the need for a comprehensive analysis of the internal and external environment of the enterprise, taking into account industry characteristics and ensuring the flexibility of the strategy in the conditions of market changes [3; 9]. These approaches become especially relevant in crisis conditions, when marketing strategies

must ensure a rapid response to risks, minimize losses and maintain the financial stability of enterprises.

Issues of anti-crisis management of enterprises are studied in the works of modern Ukrainian scientists. In particular, the works of Yu. Aleskerova and co-authors substantiate the importance of financial planning as a tool for minimizing risks [1], and also reveal the theoretical and methodological aspects of anti-crisis financial management [2]. Research by O. A. Smetanyuk et al. are devoted to the management of anti-crisis processes at enterprises [11], while A. Marachevska focuses on the practical value of anti-crisis management in the conditions of the war and post-war period in Ukraine [13].

A separate area of research concerns the specifics of the functioning of enterprises in the agricultural sector. Thus, the works of V. A. Mamchur and N. V. Germaniuk consider methodological approaches to assessing the development of entrepreneurship in agriculture [12]. Researchers emphasize the influence of seasonality of production, dependence on natural and climatic conditions, perishability of products and high price volatility on the activities of enterprises, which necessitates the formation of adaptive marketing strategies.

The financial aspects of the functioning of enterprises in modern conditions are also reflected in the works of L. Fedoryshyna and co-authors, who study the issues of financial control of small businesses [5] and the impact of imbalances in the economic space on the financial mechanism of the enterprise [6]. These studies emphasize the importance of integrating financial and marketing instruments to ensure the stability of enterprises.

Modern scientific approaches also focus on the digitalization of marketing activities, the use of CRM and ERP systems, data analytics and e-commerce as tools for improving the efficiency of enterprise management. At the same time, the implementation of such solutions requires the use of a project approach that ensures a clear structuring of processes, effective allocation of resources and control of results.

At the same time, the analysis of scientific sources indicates the presence of a number of unresolved issues. In particular, the aspects of integrating marketing strategies into the anti-crisis management system of agricultural enterprises remain insufficiently studied, which limits the possibilities of timely response to risks and instability of the external environment. The mechanism for combining strategic marketing with risk management tools requires further development.

In addition, the issue of effective application of the project approach to the development and implementation of marketing strategies remains relevant, in particular regarding the structuring of processes, allocation of resources and evaluation of results. Insufficient attention has been paid to the formation of methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of marketing strategies, taking into account the dynamics of the market environment.

Thus, there is an objective need for further development of the theoretical and methodological principles of forming and implementing marketing strategies based on the integration of the concepts of strategic marketing, crisis management, and a project approach, which will contribute to increasing the efficiency of the functioning of agricultural enterprises in conditions of uncertainty and risks.

Statement of main research material. In modern economic conditions, a marketing strategy serves as a key tool for ensuring a company's competitiveness, focused on meeting consumer needs, and achieving long-term development goals. For agricultural enterprises, whose operations depend on environmental and climatic factors, seasonal production, and market fluctuations, developing an effective marketing strategy is not only an economic necessity but also a crucial condition for ensuring stability, adaptability, and sustainable growth.

In the conditions of the increased uncertainty and risk, marketing strategy takes on particular importance as a component of anti-crisis management, as it enables companies to respond promptly to shifts in demand, adapt their distribution channels, optimize their product range and pricing policies, and minimize the negative impact of external threats.

In a corporate management system, the marketing strategy serves as a coordinating element that integrates the functions of planning, organization, motivation, and control. Its significance lies in: identifying strategic directions for the company's development in line with market trends; improving the efficiency of production, financial, and human resources; building long-term relationships with customers, partners, and suppliers; strengthening the company's image and reputation. The main types of marketing strategies used in agriculture include (see table 1).

Table 1

The main types of marketing strategies used in agriculture

Type of marketing strategy	Essence of strategy	Main goals and objectives	Expected outcomes for agricultural enterprise
Product differentiation strategy	Creating a unique value proposition based on product quality, sustainability, natural ingredients, or origin of products	Building competitive advantages, brand development, and increasing customer loyalty	Boost in market share, selling price increase, and enhancing reputation of the manufacturer
Pricing strategy	Determining the optimal price for products, considering production costs, solvency of consumers, and competitors' actions	Ensuring competitiveness, optimizing profitability, increasing sales volume	Increase in revenue, stability of sales, establishing of price flexing
Sale strategy	Development and improvement of sales channels, logistics networks, and cooperation with intermediaries and partners	Reducing transportation costs and increasing product availability for consumers	Marketing development, increase of efficiency of logistics, reduction of product losses
Communication strategy	Building an effective system of marketing communications: advertising, PR, branding, social media	Building a positive image, promoting brand, attracting new customers	Increase company recognition, rise in demand, strengthening business reputation
Strategy of innovative development	Implementation of digital technologies, CRM and ERP systems, automation of marketing processes, and use of e-commerce	Improving management efficiency, reducing costs, and quick adaptation to the market	Increase productivity, digital transformation of the business, sustainable development of the enterprise

Source: compiled by the authors based on their own research

Strategic planning of marketing activities is particularly important for the agricultural sector, as it considers the specific characteristics of agricultural products (perishability, seasonality, dependence on weather conditions, significant price fluctuations, etc.). Under such conditions, a marketing strategy must combine elements of market adaptation with innovative approaches to managing production and distribution processes and risks.

In modern conditions, the implementation of marketing strategies is increasingly based on project management principles, which involve clearly defining the objectives, resources, timelines, and outcomes of marketing initiatives. This approach allows for more effective implementation of strategic decisions, ensures control over their execution, and enables a flexible response to changes in the external environment, which is particularly important in crisis situations.

The use of marketing strategies within the management system of an agricultural enterprise helps ensure synergy between production, sales, and consumption, focusing the enterprise's activities on meeting demand and establishing a stable market position [10].

From a strategic perspective, a marketing strategy serves as a comprehensive platform for managerial decisions, integrating market analysis, demand forecasting, innovative product development, and customer relationship management. Its implementation establishes a solid foundation for a company's economic growth, market expansion, and overall management efficiency. This takes on particular significance in times of instability when marketing strategy becomes a vital tool for ensuring the company's adaptability and resilience [9].

In the context of anti-crisis management, a marketing strategy ensures the timely identification of market threats and opportunities, enables the reassessment of target segments, optimizes the product portfolio, and facilitates the development of new sales channels. This helps mitigate the impact of crisis factors and enhances the flexibility of management decisions.

As a practical matter, having a clear marketing strategy enables a company to achieve several promising goals at once (Fig. 1). It serves as a systematic management tool that integrates analytical, communication, production, and sales components into a single, coherent model for the company's development.

Fig. 1. The benefits of implementing marketing strategy in a company

Source: compiled by the authors based on their own research

Developing an effective marketing strategy is a complex, multi-step process that requires a systematic approach, in-depth market analysis, and a clear definition of the company's goals. In today's dynamic business environment, strategic planning is of critical importance, as it enables a company not only to adapt to changes but also to stay ahead of them, building its own competitive advantages and ensuring long-term stability. [1].

An important aspect of modern marketing strategy development is the use of project management tools, which involves breaking down the process of strategy development and implementation into distinct phases, identifying responsible parties, allocating resources, and establishing performance evaluation criteria. This approach allows for greater control over the strategic planning process, ensures monitoring of goal achievement, and minimizes risks, which is particularly relevant in times of crisis.

Following the stages of marketing strategy development in sequence ensures that the strategy aligns with the company's overall development strategy, enables optimal resource allocation, and enhances the effectiveness of management decisions. Each stage has its own objectives, tools, and expected outcomes, which form a comprehensive system for managing marketing activities and create the conditions for the effective implementation of the strategy (Table 2).

Table 2

Stages of formation and implementation of effective marketing strategy of agricultural enterprises

Stage	Essentiality of the stage	Main tools and results
1. Analysis of external and internal environment	Comprehensive diagnostics of the market situation, consumers, competitors, and the enterprise resource potential.	SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, competitive analysis, and market research. The result is the identification of the company's opportunities, threats, and strengths.
2. Determination of strategic marketing goals	Establishing long-term marketing goals in line with the company's mission and vision.	Setting SMART goals (market share, profitability, brand awareness, entering new markets, etc.).
3. Development of strategic alternatives	Identifying potential areas of development and strategic ways to achieve goals.	Development of strategies: differentiation, cost leadership, focus, and innovation. Effect: the selection of the most appropriate direction.
4. Selection and implementation of the strategy	Deciding on the optimal strategy and implementing it in business operations.	Budget planning, selection of marketing tools (4P/7P), coordination of departments, implementation of CRM/ERP systems.
5. Control, evaluation, and adjustment	Measuring the results of the marketing strategy, identifying deviations, and making adjustments.	Analysis of KPI, ROI, market share, and customer loyalty. Effect: improving efficiency and adaptation of the strategy to market changes.

Source: compiled by the authors based on their own research

Therefore, the development of marketing strategy should be viewed not as a one-time managerial act, but as a continuous, cyclical process that combines analytical, planning, organizational, and control functions. This approach ensures timely adjustments to strategic objectives in line with changes in the market environment and

enables the company to maintain a high level of adaptability and management effectiveness in the long term.

In conditions of instability and growing risks, marketing strategy takes on particular importance as a component of anti-crisis management, since its flexibility and adaptability ensure a timely response to crises, mitigate the negative impact of external factors, and preserve the company's competitive position. [4].

At the same time, the effective implementation of marketing strategies increasingly relies on project management tools, which help structure the process of executing strategic initiatives and define clear stages, resources, timelines, and responsible parties. This approach ensures greater control over the implementation process, monitoring of results, and minimization of risks which is particularly important in crisis conditions of enterprises functioning.

Based on an analysis of the practical experience of Ukrainian and foreign companies, several examples can be identified that demonstrate the impact of strategic marketing on business performance. In particular, the effective application of strategies for differentiation, innovative development, branding, or partnership cooperation allows for increased competitiveness, optimized costs, strengthened market positions, and long-term stability. In the context of anti-crisis management, such strategies serve as a tool not only for survival but also for the development of the enterprise.

Thus, a marketing strategy is not merely a conceptual document, but a full-fledged management tool that takes on practical significance during implementation and ensures the transformation of the company's potential into tangible economic results. [15].

To gain a clearer understanding of how it is applied, it is advisable to analyze various types of marketing strategies, their substantive characteristics, and the management outcomes achieved during their implementation. In this context, marketing strategies also serve as a crisis response tool, helping to reduce risks and increase the adaptability of enterprises.

Table 3 provides an overview of the most common types of marketing strategies, their areas of practical application, and expected outcomes, considering their potential use in the context of anti-crisis management and project implementation.

Table 3

Examples of the practical significance of marketing strategies in the agricultural enterprise management

Type of marketing strategy	Essentiality and practical implementation	Results and management impact
Product differentiation strategy	Focus on the product's unique properties: eco-friendliness, quality, and regional origin. Implementation of certifications (EU Organic, ISO 22000) and creation of own trademark for farm products.	Increase in selling prices by 20–30%, entry into premium markets, growth in consumer confidence, and increase in competitiveness.
Innovative marketing strategy	Use of digital management technologies: CRM, ERP, Big Data, and online sales. Optimization of planning, communication, and sales processes.	Reduction in communication costs by 10-15 %, improvement of demand forecasting, enhance of management efficiency, and increase of customer loyalty.
Communication strategy (branding and CSR)	Building a positive corporate image through advertising, public relations, social media marketing, participation in social projects, and corporate social responsibility.	Increasing brand awareness, enhancing customer loyalty, improving corporate reputation, and stabilizing market position.
Strategy of partnership and cooperation	Establishing associations of small and medium-sized enterprises for co-marketing, logistics, export, and procurement.	Cost optimization, strengthening bargaining power in the market, increasing sales volumes, improving profitability and sustainable growth.
Competitive pricing strategy	Formation of the optimal price/quality ration, utilizing flexible discounts, and implementing price differentiation for various market segments	Increasing sales, attracting new customers, stabilizing revenue, and maintaining market position in a highly competitive environment.

Source: compiled by the authors based on their own research

Thus, the practical significance of marketing strategies lies in enhancing a company's competitiveness, improving management efficiency, and ensuring its long-term stability. Their competent implementation allows not only for achieving positive financial results but also for building sustainable strategic advantages in the market, which is particularly relevant in the context of Ukraine's economic transformation and rising levels of uncertainty [2]. In this context, marketing strategies also serve as a crisis response tool, helping to reduce risks and increase the adaptability of enterprises.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, it was found that a marketing strategy is a key tool for business management, enabling the company to adapt to changes in the market environment and develop competitive advantages. It has been demonstrated that the effective implementation of marketing strategies contributes to increasing profitability, optimizing resource utilization, expanding sales markets, and strengthening corporate image. It was determined that the process of forming a marketing strategy has a complex, systematic and cyclical nature, involves a combination of analytical, planning and control functions, and requires taking into account industry specifics, in particular the characteristics of the agricultural sector. The need for active use of modern digital technologies, data analytics and innovative marketing tools that increase the effectiveness of management decisions is substantiated. It has been proven that in the conditions of crisis phenomena and instability of the external environment, marketing strategies act as an important element of the anti-crisis management system, ensuring management flexibility, timely response to market changes and reducing the negative impact of risks. It has been established that the effective implementation of marketing strategies is achieved under the condition of using project management tools that allow structuring the process of their implementation, ensuring a rational distribution of resources, control of results and achievement of strategic goals within the specified time frame. [6].

Thanks to marketing strategies, the enterprise can adapt to changes in the external environment, determine priority areas of development, optimize the use of resources and create sustainable competitive advantages that ensure stable economic

growth and sustainable development, especially in the conditions of transformation of the economy of Ukraine.

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